

Milestone MS6

**Agreement of boundaries for a
set of regionalisation
approaches for a choice of
ocean indicators**

MILESTONE

Milestone	MS6 Agreement of boundaries for a set of regionalisation approaches for a choice of ocean indicators
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1. Means of verification

As stated in the ObsSea4Clim Description of the Action, the means to verify that this milestone has been achieved is " an agreed set of regions and indicators." The description of this set and the agreement process is detailed below.

2. Regionalisation of climate indicators

2.1 The need for regionalised climate indicators

Global climate indicators are key parameters used to describe and monitor the changing climate e.g. https://climatedata-catalogue-wmo.org/climate_indicators. They provide a picture of the state of the climate system and help track climate change across different domains. Some of the main global climate indicators include mean surface temperature, mean sea level, ocean heat content, and sea ice extent. One of the challenges in ObsSea4Clim is to regionalise these indicators.

Regionalised climate indicators offer many benefits, including helping understand how various regions exhibit unique environmental and climatic patterns, understanding the specific factors driving these differences, and how they relate to global trends. By equipping policymakers and stakeholders with accurate and region-specific data, regionalised climate indicators can effectively support the development of tailored policies that address local environmental challenges, thus elevating essential ocean observations to the science and policy interface (von Schuckmann et al., 2020).

This milestone is to document the agreements made on:

1. An initial set of regions for indicators
2. An initial set of essential ocean variables for indicators

2.2 Process of agreement

A meeting of ObsSea4Clim partners was convened on the 5th of July 2024 to agree on a set of regionalisations and variables. The meeting also discussed the scientific requirements surrounding regionalisation, including the underlying oceanic and climatic dynamics that contributed to these differences. This aimed to enhance our understanding of the mechanisms at play.

Attendee	Affiliation to ObsSea4Clim partner
Gerard McCarthy	NUIM
Catherine O Beirne	NUIM
Samantha Hallam	NUIM
Paul Hargous	CSIC
Haapala Jari	FMI
Francois Counillon	NERSC
Inga Lips	EUROGOOS
Ronan McAdam	CMCC
Dimitra Denaxa	HCMR
Steffen M. Olsen	DMI

Table 1: Attendees and affiliations of meeting 5th July 2024

It was highlighted that remote regions had far-reaching impacts and that this was key for communicating the importance of climate indicators that may at first seem removed from the region of interest. For example, a slowdown in the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) could lead to significant climatic changes in

Europe, including cooler temperatures and altered weather patterns. Warmer than average ocean temperatures in North America can have cascading effects on the climate and marine ecosystems in Europe, influencing weather patterns, fish migration, and the overall health of marine biodiversity, which impacts the fishing industry and coastal communities. The extent and condition of Arctic sea ice play a crucial role in regulating the climate of mid-latitude regions. Changes in sea ice could disrupt atmospheric circulation patterns, leading to extreme weather events and shifts in seasonal climate norms. Additionally, changes in ocean circulation leading to Atlantification in the Arctic, where warmer Atlantic waters penetrated the Arctic Ocean, has altered its temperature and salinity. This has profoundly affected Arctic ecosystems, ice cover, and, potentially, global climate patterns, highlighting the interconnectedness of regional and global systems.

2.3 Agreed Regions

For each EOVI which will be analysed: sea surface temperature (SST), subsurface temperature, sea surface height, and sea ice, the proposed indicators were identified through discussions and meetings and are detailed in the tables below. Indicators are 'A simple easy-to-understand tool to describe, measure and monitor a complex ocean phenomenon.' (von Schuckmann et al., 2020) For each indicator, the proposed regions were identified, including both the global perspective, where relevant, and then progressively smaller regions and seas. Thematic regions are also included for some indicators. Legislative exclusive economic zones (EEZ) will be analysed in specific case studies (Ireland and Finland) for SST. The main hurricane development region in the Atlantic (10–20° N and 20–60° W) will be analysed for SST and ocean heat content as there are direct links with rising ocean temperatures and hurricane intensity in the Atlantic.

2.3.1 Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Temperature

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions	Subregions	Case Studies
SST	SST	Mean SST	Copernicus Datasets Observational datasets including HadISST, and DCENT.	1980-present 1850-present	Northeast Atlantic Ocean and the adjacent Seas [MOI] North Atlantic [NUIM]	Mediterranean [MOI] Black Sea [MOI] Baltic [MOI] IBI* [MOI] Nordic [DMI, HAV] Barents Sea [NERSC]	Legislative Bounds (EEZ, territorial waters): Ireland and Finland [NUIM, FMI] Thematic (Hurricane Main development Region) [NUIM]
SST	SST and sea ice temperature	Mean SST/IST	C3S Global L4 SST/IST	1982-present	Arctic/Antarctic/global [DMI]		

*IBI = Ireland, Biscay, Iberia

Table 2: Agreed Sea Surface Temperature variables and regions

The EOVs and associated indicators have been broken down into smaller regions as relevant; the North Atlantic Ocean (Fig 2. A), the Northeastern Atlantic and Adjacent seas (Fig 2. B), the Arctic Ocean (Fig 3. A), and the Antarctic Ocean (Fig 3. B),. Figure 4 (A) shows a breakdown of the Northeastern Atlantic and adjacent seas in subregions, with case study regions shown in Fig 4B. Reference shapefiles for these regions can be found in Table 3.

Fig. 2: Maps of regions referred to in the text: (A) North Atlantic Ocean (red) with the Main Development Region for Hurricanes (Black box) and Gulf Stream Region (Blue box) highlighted. (B) Northeastern Atlantic and adjacent seas (orange). Ref: <https://sp.copernicus.org/articles/4-osr8/2/2024/>

Fig. 3: Extent of regions (A) Arctic Oceans (another common definition is $>60^{\circ}\text{N}$) and (B) Antarctic Ocean ($>60^{\circ}\text{S}$).

Fig. 4: Sub-regions referred to in the text. (A) North Sea (cyan), IBI (yellow, IBI = Ireland Biscay Iberia = OSPAR regions III, IV, V), Mediterranean Sea (purple), Black Sea (orange), Baltic Sea (pink), Nordic Sea (dark orange), Barents Sea (dark green). (B) Case studies referred to in the text: Irish continental shelf (red line) and EEZ (green), Finnish EEZ (cyan).

Table 3: References for regions referred to in the text.

Region/Subregion	Link to shapefile
North Atlantic	https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=1912
Northeastern Atlantic and adjacent seas	https://sp.copernicus.org/articles/4-osr8/2/2024/
Mediterranean	https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=1905
Arctic Ocean	https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=1906
Antarctic Ocean	https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=1907
Nordic Sea	https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=2353

Barents Sea	https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=4247
Baltic Sea	Marine Regions · Baltic Sea (IHO Sea Area)
IBI- OSPAR Region	https://odims.ospar.org/en/submissions/ospar_regions_2017_01/
Black Sea	Marine Regions · Black Sea (IHO Sea Area)
Ireland EEZ	Marine Regions · Irish Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ)
Ireland Real Map	The Real Map of Ireland - Download shapefile - data.gov.ie
Finnish EEZ	Marine Regions · Finnish Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ)

EOV/ECV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice Surface temperature	Sea Ice Surface Temperature	Mean IST	AASTI/C3S L3/L4 [DMI]	1982-present	Arctic/Antarctic sea ice [DMI]
			neXtSIM reanalysis, Copernicus datasets	1996-present	Arctic [NERSC]
Sea Ice Surface temperature	Melt Days	Days when the mean temperature is 0 °C or warmer	AASTI/C3S L3/L4 [DMI]	1982-present	Arctic/Antarctic sea ice [DMI]
Sea Ice Surface temperature	Freezing degree days (FDD)	The cumulative FDD is usually calculated as a sum of average daily degrees below freezing	AASTI/C3S L3/L4 [DMI]	1982-present	Arctic/Antarctic sea ice [DMI]

Table 4: Variables and Regions associated with Sea Ice Surface Temperature.

2.3.2 Subsurface Temperature

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions	Subregions	Case Studies and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Subsurface Temperature	Ocean Heat Content	Ocean Heat Content	Copernicus reanalysis - global and regional	1980-present (satellite)	NE Atlantic Ocean and adjacent seas [MOI] North Atlantic [MOI] Global [MOI and others]	Mediterranean [MOI] Barents Sea [NERSC] Black Sea [MOI] Baltic [MOI] IBI [MOI] Nordic [DMI, HAV] NWS [MOI]	MDR [NUIM] Gulf Stream/AMOC and Atlantic OHC [NUIM]
Subsurface Temperature	Marine Heatwaves	Subsurface Temperatures	Copernicus reanalysis - regional	1982-present	Mediterranean Sea [CMCC]		Subsurface marine heatwaves
				1993-present	Baltic Sea [FMI] Barents Sea [NERSC]		

*precise definition of subsurface MHWs (e.g. using OHC) will be dependent on the findings of 3.2

Table 5: Variables and Regions associated with Sub-surface Temperature.

2.3.3 Sea Ice

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Concentration	Satellite-derived sea ice concentration	OSI-450a Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSM/I/SSMIS), release 3	1978-present (incl iCDR)	Arctic and Antarctic sea Ice [DMI]
			OSI-458 Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (AMSR), release 3	2002-present (incl iCDR)	
			ESA Sea Ice CCI: High(er) Resolution Sea Ice Concentration CDR, v3	1991-2020	

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
			NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1979-present	
		neXtSIM reanalysis	Copernicus Marine Services	1996-present	Arctic and Antarctic sea Ice [NERSC]
		Satellite Passive microwave	Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSM/I/SSMIS)	1978-present	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
		SAR	Sentinel-radar backscatter	Available images from 2014	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
		SAR	EOS-04 RISAT-1 radar backscatter	Available images from 2012	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
		Satellite passive microwave	NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1979-present	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
		Global reanalysis ensemble product	Copernicus Marine Services	1993-present	Arctic and Antarctic [CMCC]
		Satellite-derived	SIC from NOAA/NSIDC CDR, OSI SAF, ESA, CCI	1979-present/2002-2017	Arctic and Antarctic [CMCC]

Table 6: Variables and Regions associated with Sea Ice Concentration

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Extent	Satellite passive microwave	OSI-SAF version 3, Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMRR, SSMI, SSMIS)	1978-present	Antarctic sea ice [NCPOR]
		Satellite Passive Microwave	NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice concentration, version 4	1979-present	
		Satellite-derived; ocean reanalysis and forecast	Arctic OMI SI extent obs, satellite observations	1979-present(satellite) 1993-present (forecast and reanalysis)	Arctic and Antarctic [MOI]
			OSI SAF Sea ice index 1978-onwards, version 2.2 (2023), OSI-420. EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility.		
			Antarctic_OMI_SI_extent_obs, satellite observations		

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
			OSI SAF Sea ice index 1978-onwards, version 2.2 (2023), OSI-420. EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility.		
			GLOBAL_MULTIYEAR_PHY_001_030, numerical models & GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_001_024		
		Satellite-derived	OSI-450a Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSM/I/SSMIS), release 3	1978-present (incl iCDR)	Arctic and Antarctic sea ice [DMI]
			OSI-458 Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (AMSR), release 3	2002-present (incl iCDR)	
			ESA Sea Ice CCI: High(er) Resolution Sea Ice Concentration CDR, v3	1991-2020	

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EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
			NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1979-present	

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Drift	neXtSIM reanalysis	Copernicus Marine Services	1996-present	Arctic [NERSC]
		Buoy	IABP	1979-present	Arctic[FMI]
		Satellite Passive Microwave	Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSMI/SSMIS)	1978-present	Antarctic sea ice [NCPOR]
		SAR	Sentinel-radar backscatter EOS-04, RISAT-1 radar backscatter	Available images since 2014 Available images since 2012	Antarctic sea ice [NCPOR]
		Satellite passive microwave	NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1979-present	Antarctic sea ice [NCPOR]
Sea Ice	Sea Ice thickness	In-situ observations	FMI monitoring programme	1898-present	Baltic/Bay of Bothnia [FMI]
		Global reanalysis ensemble product	Copernicus Marine Services	1993-present	Arctic and Antarctic [CMCC]

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Age	Satellite Derived	Copernicus Marine Services	1996-present	Arctic [NERSC]
		neXtSIM reanalysis	Copernicus Marine Services	1996-present	Arctic [NERSC]
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Area	Satellite Passive Microwave	Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSMI/SSMIS)	1978-present	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
		SAR	Sentinel-radar backscatter	Available images from 2014	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
		SAR	EOS-04, RISAT-1 radar backscatter	Available images from 2012	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]
	Satellite Passive Microwave	NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1979-present	Antarctic Sea Ice [NCPOR]	
	Sea Ice Area/	Satellite-derived	OSI-450a Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (SMMR/SSMI/SSMIS), release 3	1978-present (incl iCDR)	Arctic and Antarctic sea ice [DMI]

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions / Subregion and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
	Freezeup/Break update/ Open water days		OSI-458 Global Sea Ice Concentration climate data record (AMSR), release 3	2002-present (incl iCDR)	
			ESA Sea Ice CCI: High(er) Resolution Sea Ice Concentration CDR, v3	1991-2020	
			NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration, Version 4	1979-present	
Sea Ice	Freezing Date/ Break update	In-situ observations	FMI monitoring programme	1898-present	Baltic/Bay of Bothnia
Sea Ice	Sea Ice Volume	neXtSIM	Copernicus Marine Services	1996-present	Arctic [NERSC]

Table 7: Variables and Regions associated with other Sea Ice Indicators.

2.3.4 Sea Surface Height

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions	Subregions	Case Studies and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Surface Height	Sea Level	Mean Sea Level	Copernicus Satellite Observations (Global and regional OMI_SL) Reanalysis	1980-present 1950-present 1993-present	NE Atlantic Oceans and adjacent seas [MOI] Nordic and Barents Seas	Mediterranean [MOI] Barents Sea [NERSC] Black Sea [MOI] Baltic[MOI] IBI[MOI] Nordic[HAV, DMI] NWS[MOI]	Coastlines e.g.national/regional Link between data e.g. Irish [NUIM]
Sea Surface Height	Sea level	Mass Component of Sea Level	GRACE GRACE/FO	2002-2017 2018-present	Global	Norwegian Continental shelf [NERSC] Arctic Ocean [NERSC]	Quantify open ocean contribution Norwegian sea level variations

EOV	Indicator	Measure	Data	Timeframe	Regions	Subregions	Case Studies and ObsSea4Clim partner in lead
Sea Surface Height	In-situ Sea Level	Tide Gauge	Monthly averaged tide gauge data (PSMSL)	1800-present (but not complete)	Global coastline	Arctic Ocean	Assess the quality of the Arctic Ocean Physics reanalysis Topaz4b
			10 minute tide gauge data (Kartverket)	late 1980s-present (but not complete)	Norwegian Coast	Western Norway Central Norway	1) Assess quality of satellite altimetry products (e.g., SWOT), if possible, during extreme sea-level conditions (e.g., during the passage of a storm) 2) Characterize mesoscale variability over the Norwegian continental shelf (e.g., identify the presence of coastal trapped waves along the coast of Norway)

Table 8: Variables and Regions associated with Sea Surface Height.

3. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

This milestone contributes to achieving the following specific objectives of the project.

#SO1	To develop ocean indicators, provide improved EO/ECVs and evolve European ocean observing
This milestone is instrumental to achieving this SO, as it is linked to the D3.1 and D3.2 that will come in later.	
SO2	To advance the use of EO/ECVs for improved ESM and reduced uncertainty in projections
Climate indicators such as SST and SSH are used to validate climate projections. As projections focus on regions, the regionalisation approach to indicators will help inform the validation of model results.	
SO3	To create an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs
This milestone is instrumental to the achievement of this SO, as it is linked to the D3.3 that will come in later.	
SO5	To place Europe in the forefront of the global coordination of the broader ocean-climate nexus

This milestone is instrumental to achieving this SO, as it is linked to the D3.1-D3.3 that will come in later. Regionalising climate indicators is the next step in communicating the ocean-climate nexus to policymakers and the public.

4. References

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